

OR in the industrial engineering of Industry 4.0 - Experiences from the Iberian Peninsula mirrored in CJOR

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Abstract

Industry 4.0 (I4.0) implies a group of technologies, organizational concepts and management principles to improve the performance of manufacturing companies or supply chains driven by production cost optimization, mass customization requirements, connectivity and digitization of factories. The purpose of this paper is to relate Iberian Peninsula advances in I4.0 from Spanish and Portuguese research works published in CJOR papers. Hence this paper reviews the Spanish and Portuguese operations research (OR) and industrial engineering-based papers published in CJOR from 2011, when the I4.0 concept emerged, to the present-day. Here 47 papers are reviewed according to classification criteria based on the following elements: (1) objectives; (2) application context; (3) modeling approach; (4) development or software tool; (5) I4.0 technologies. The main outcomes, limitations and further research are also identified for recent papers. Finally, research trends and future directions in industrial engineering, OR and I4.0 are discussed.

Keywords: Industry 4.0, Industrial Engineering, Iberian Peninsula, ICIEM, ADINGOR.

1. INTRODUCTION

Industrial engineering studies are the branch of engineering studies concerned about the analysis, design, organization and control of production and service systems. In these first studies, researchers work on the challenges of manufacturing plant analysis, designing and control by considering mostly the operating efficiency of human resources and machines. These studies include these activities: production planning, organization and control; quality statistics and control; inventory optimization and warehouse design; equipment and maintenance; optimal plant layout and workstation design.

Operations research (OR) methods and models as applied mathematics lie in implementation areas in many disciplines, and also in industrial engineering. As a multidisciplinary applied science it utilizes algebra and optimization, probability and statistics, analyses in real and transformed spaces which, in industrial engineering, have led to many new approaches; for example, machine learning and other methods. Today's industrial engineering challenges are more broadly spread, but concentrate on productivity and all the technical problems of production management and control, as well as financial and general economic consequences. OR methods can be found in all kinds of industrial organization from manufacturing to distribution, transportation, other logistics, and services. Industrial engineers' duties are wide-ranging, from the design of single operations to that of the management and control of complete production, logistics and other service systems. Their systems not only involve physical issues, but also integrate them into financial, general economic and environmental components. One important challenge is engineering solutions in benefit of human resources by designing their working places and combining their activities with collaborative robots, modernized workstations and others. Then there are ergonomic solutions for which OR methods and models are essential for organizations to make profits and providing workers with benefits.

In Spain, PhD programs oriented to industrial production and engineering with a solid OR support are based mainly on previous Bachelor (Mula et al. 2012) and/or Master studies in Organization Engineering. There are currently 17 Master degrees in Spain in the engineering and architecture branch related to production, logistics and/or supply chain engineering. Four Polytechnic Universities offer seven of these Master's degrees: Polytechnic University of Cartagena (1), Polytechnic University of Madrid (2), Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (2) and Universitat Politècnica de València (2). About 10 main PhD programs that focus on industrial production and engineering are offered by Spanish universities. The Spanish Association for the Development of Organization Engineering (ADINGOR) is integrating and disseminating Organization Engineering knowledge through, among others, the annual International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Industrial Management (ICIEIM) or CIO (Congreso en Ingeniería de Organización) conferences, whose selected better results obtained since 2017 are published in CJOR special issues (Mula and Bogataj, 2020). In Portugal, there are five main PhD programs about industrial engineering and OR methodologies: Industrial Engineering and Management (Aveiro); Leaders for Industrial Techniques (Lisbon); Industrial and Systems Engineering (Minho); Engineering and Industrial Management (Porto); and Advanced Engineering Systems for Industry (Minho). The overall objective of these Master's and PhD degrees is to train practitioners and researchers in advanced production engineering, logistics and supply chains by orienting their training toward company requirements or choosing a research itinerary. Advanced planning, programming and sequencing techniques are addressed in both an industrial and supply chain context. Supply and distribution logistics techniques, logistics and supply chain

engineering, and their strategies, are also studied. Finally, process management, performance measurement systems, and modeling and simulation techniques for production, logistics and supply chain systems are investigated and applied.

Regarding the international development of industrial engineering and OR solutions, according to the Journal Citation Report 2019, the Engineering, Industrial scientific category, with 48 journals, has an aggregate impact factor of 3.893, while Operations Research & Management Science, with 83 journals, has one of 3.176. Here it is important to highlight that 18 of 48 Industrial Engineering journals also belong to the Operations Research & Management Science category, which shows that the growth of both disciplines is closely related.

From an operations management perspective, Industry 4.0 (I4.0) is a connection of technologies, organizational concepts and management principles that underlies a cost-efficient, responsive, resilient and sustainable supply chain (Ivanov et al. 2020; Cañas et al. 2020; Fortuny-Santos et al. 2020). The main enabling technologies for I4.0 development are: additive manufacturing, artificial intelligence and machine learning, autonomous vehicles and mobile robots, big data and data analytics, blockchain, cloud computing and cloud manufacturing, cyber-physical systems (CPS), cyber security, digital twins, Internet of Things (IoT) and Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), optimization, real-time communication, RFID, simulation, social media analytics and tracking and tracing systems (TTS). While I4.0 focuses on practice and research, Ivanov et al. (2020) argue that operations management studies in this area are not progressive enough. Therefore, with their paper they intended to understand the current I4.0 research state in different disciplines and to gain insights and opportunities for future research in operations management. They provided a focused analysis to examine the state of the art and learned about researchers' perspectives in I4.0 by offering a global survey on I4.0 topics with researchers in operations management, OR, industrial engineering and control and data science, which was presented at the 9th IFAC MIM 2019 conference, where the current state of knowledge and research opportunities for I4.0 was discussed.

OR and industrial engineering are two main research disciplines involved in I4.0, together with control, data science, mechanical engineering and supply chain operations management. Cañas and Mula (2020) identify that the majority of research works published in the I4.0-based production management and engineering context center on the production programming of flow workshops and supply chain planning. In this paper, we provide an overview of recent results from I4.0-based OR and industrial engineering applications carried out in the Iberian Peninsula and mirrored in CJOR articles. The main motivation is to identify current trends and new research to be conducted in Spain and Portugal in relation to industrial engineering, OR and I4.0.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 and Section 3 present a short literature review about Iberian Peninsula CJOR articles and relate them to I4.0 technologies. Section 4 discusses the main findings of the review. Section 5 presents the conclusions and further research.

2. IBERIAN PENINSULA MIRRORED IN CJOR ARTICLES – THE CONTRIBUTIONS BEFORE 2021

Before 2011, when the first idea about I4.0 came about, only five Spanish and three Portuguese articles were published in CJOR, and studied the efficiency and competitions of football teams, from the data envelopment analysis (DEA) (Garcia-Sanchez, 2007; Guzman and Morrow, 2007; Picazo-Tadeo and Gonzalez-Gomez, 2010) to game theoretical approaches, by comparing Shapley and Owen values (Lopez and Saboya, 2009) and also discussing business technical efficiency matters (Garcia-Sanchez, 2010). Additionally, the first CJOR papers from Portugal were more orientated to routing and location problems (Craveirinha et al. 2008; Dias et al. 2008) by presenting the proposal of a multi-objective routing optimization framework for multiprotocol label switching (MPLS) networks and a capacitated dynamic location problem. Witte and Marques (2010) strike a balance between economies of scale and a sufficient number of remaining comparable utilities using DEA by comparing the efficiency of the drinking water sector in the Netherlands, England and Wales, Australia, Portugal and Belgium. Since 2011, ideas about I4.0 are also reflected in some CJOR articles. During the 2011-2021 period, we identified 47 Spanish and Portuguese papers published in CJOR (Table 1).

Table 1. Spanish and Portuguese papers in CJOR since 2011.

	2011-2015	2016-2020	2021	Total
Spain	7	19	12	38
Portugal	7	1	1	9
Total	14	20	13	47

Table 2 provides a general review of the articles published during the 2011-2020 period, along with their modeling approaches and major outcomes. These papers have been reviewed and classified according to the following criterias: objectives of the paper; application context; modeling approach; software tool used; I4.0 technologies contributed.

Table 2. Spanish and Portuguese papers in CJOR 2011-2020.

Authors (year)	Objectives	Application context	Modeling Approach	Software tools	I4.0 technologies contributed
Belen et al. (2011)	To explain rumour spreading in continuous time	Rumours	Differential equations	MAPLE	Simulation
Simoos and Marques (2011)	To measure the efficiency or congestion of Portuguese hospitals	Health	DEA	Not mentioned	Optimization
Baptista and Oliveira (2012)	To evaluate dispatching rules for the Lisbon emergency medical system	Health	Queuing theory	Visual Basic - Excel	Simulation
Pedamallu et al. (2012)	To model HIV/AIDS transmission	Health	Cross impact analysis – dynamical system	Not mentioned	Simulation
Pinto et al. (2012)	To model a financial market under uncertainty	Financial market	Random game matching – dynamical system	Not mentioned	Simulation
Ros-McDonnell et al. (2012)	To maximize the efficiency of using different means of transport and loading	Logistics	Branch and bound heuristics	Not mentioned	Optimization
Volkovich et al. (2012)	To propose a minimal spanning tree approach for the cluster	Data mining	Clustering methods	Not mentioned	Machine learning

Authors (year)	Objectives	Application context	Modeling Approach	Software tools	I4.0 technologies contributed
	validation problem				
Garcia-Sanchez et al. (2013)	To analyse the efficiency of police forces in Spain	Police services	DEA	FEAR	Optimization
Lopez-Perez and Rodriguez-Ariza (2013)	To analyse the governance structure of capital international joint ventures	Spanish-Moroccan SMEs	Exploratory cross-sectional Questionnaires and statistics	Not mentioned	Data analytics
Alvarez-Diez et al. (2014)	To assess executive stock options (ESO)	Financial market	ESO analytic models: Black–Scholes (BS) and Cvitanic–Wiener–Zapatero (CWZ)	ExecuCom and Compustat databases	Data analytics
Castro et al. (2014)	To solve real size stochastic slack PERT or SPERT problems	Project management	Polynomial algorithms	Not mentioned	Data analytics
Dias et al. (2014)	To find the best set of angles, beam angle optimization, for intensity modulated radiotherapy treatment (IMRT) planning	Health	Genetic algorithms and neural networks	MATLAB CERR DICOM RT	Optimization
Freixas and Pons (2015)	To compare the success and decisiveness of a voter in symmetric games for different consensus levels	Voting systems	Cooperative games	Not mentioned	Blockchain algorithms
Kovačič et al. (2015)	To evaluate, by the extended MRP (EMRP) theory, the impact of location and lead time on the net present value of all activities in a supply chain	Food supply chain	Input-output analysis Net present value	Not mentioned	Simulation
Albizuri and Alvarez-Mozos (2016)	To propose a new family of cost-sharing rules	Cost-sharing problems	Axiomatization	Not mentioned	Data analytics
Cordero et al. (2016)	To estimate the differences in efficiency between Spanish public and private schools	Education	Free disposal hull (FDH), robuts approach and metafrontier approach	Not mentioned	Data analytics
Fraggelli et al. (2016)	To measure the importance of factors contributing to the occurrence of an event	Ocurrence of events	Cooperative games	Not mentioned	Blockchain algorithms
Amaro-Mellado et al. (2018)	To obtain a <i>b</i> -value, that represents the relation between small and large earthquakes. A map for the Iberian Peninsula	Seismic activity	Clustering methods	ZMAP NGIS	Machine learning
Pastor et al. (2018)	To extend the use of bounds, initially proposed exclusively for additive models, to the family of directional distance function models	Agricultural data	DEA	Not mentioned	Optimization

Authors (year)	Objectives	Application context	Modeling Approach	Software tools	I4.0 technologies contributed
Ligardo-Herrera et al. (2019)	To assess stakeholders' influence on a research project in the responsible research and innovation context	Information and Communication Technology (ICT) business sector	Multicriteria decision analysis (MCDA) Analytic network process (ANP)	SuperDecisions©	Data analytics
Zapata et al. (2019)	To study a duopolistic competition model in an uncertain environment where attitudes of firms toward uncertainty are incorporated	Duopoly market	Two scenario Cournot game	Not mentioned	Blockchain algorithms
Arroyo et al. (2020)	To analyze the effect of carbon pricing policies in battery electric vehicle (BEV) penetration in the city of Madrid	Transportation	Mixed-integer linear programming (MILP)/ 48A heuristic algorithm Monte Carlo simulation	Not mentioned	Optimization simulation
Babiloni and Guijarro (2020)	To calculate the fill rate at a continuous review reorder point, order quantity (s, Q) policy in a lost sales and discrete demand context	Inventory management	Mathematical formulations	Not mentioned	Simulation
Bautista-Valhondo and Alfaro-Pozo (2020)	To propose two MILP models to extend two flow shop scheduling problems (FSP) with an overall demand plan	Automotive	MILP	IBM ILOG CPLEX	Optimization
Bildosola et al. (2020)	To obtain the characterization of big data technology, which facilitates understanding and identifies its potential	Big data	Bibliometric analysis, text mining, principal component analysis (PCA), time series	Vantage-Point R software	Big data, data analytics, machine learning
Civantos and Garcia-Algarra (2020)	To study the incident management of three live services in Europe and Latin America: IPTV, Cloud Infrastructure and managed IoT connectivity	Telecom services	Time series	Prophet, Causal Impact	Data analytics
del Rosario et al. (2020)	To highlight contributions to achieve Sustainable Development Goals	Sustainable development	Editorial review	Not identified	Optimization RFID Simulation
Leon et al. (2020)	To propose a methodology for designing maintenance systems and estimating costs	Moroccan photovoltaic rural electrification	MILP, rule-based expert system (classification tree and linear regression model)	GAMS/CPLEX	Optimization Simulation
Martin et al. (2020)	To model and solve a master production schedule (MPS) problem with	Automotive	Robust optimization	GAMS/Gurobi	Optimization

Authors (year)	Objectives	Application context	Modeling Approach	Software tools	I4.0 technologies contributed
	uncertainty related to manufacturing times				
Mateo et al. (2020)	To develop a decision support system to determine the number of hired workers by taking into account supplement characteristics, ergonomic issues and production rates	Staff planning for a printing plant	MILP, Linear regression	Not identified	Optimization
Mula and Bogataj (2020)	To provide an overview of industrial engineering and management problems from an OR perspective	Engineering digital transformation	Editorial review	Not identified	Big data, data analytics, machine learning, optimization, simulation
Rius-Sorolla et al. (2020a)	To propose a procedure to solve generic materials and operations planning (GMOP) problem with different materials and process lists	Operations planning	Lagrangian relaxation	C, Excel, GUROBI	Optimization
Rius-Sorolla et al. (2020b)	To offer a systematic review of collaborative planning for coordination mechanisms in mathematical programming models	Collaborative planning	Literature review	Not identified	Optimization
Saez-Mas et al. (2020)	To model and solve an assignment problem on an assembly line on which 70 sequencing cells have to be located in a new facility	Automotive	Discrete event simulation, local search optimization heuristics	C, SIMIO	Optimization Simulation

3 RECENT RESULTS TOWARD INDUSTRY 4.0

The papers published in 2021 are mostly written on the bases of presentations at ICIEIM conferences before 2020 and further developed for CJOR. They were reviewed and classified according to the following criteria (Table 3): objectives of the paper; research area; application context; research methodology and approach modeling; software tool used; I4.0 technologies contributed; major outcomes, limitations and further research, identified by the authors.

Table 3. Spanish and Portuguese papers in CJOR in 2021.

Authors (year)	Objectives	Application context	Modeling Approach	Software tools	I4.0 technologies contributed	Major outcomes	Limitations	Future research
Acebes et al. (2021)	To propose a new metrics to be used with both the scheduling risk analysis (SRA) and dynamic scheduling frameworks for risk analyses	Project management	Monte Carlo simulation	Not mentioned	Simulation	A new sensitivity metrics called the activity risk index (ARI), which informs about what activities contribute the most to a project's uncertainty	An educational project considered an example	Studying the network's configuration and its influence on ARI for each activity
Alvarez-Gil et al. (2021)	To model and solve a flexible job-shop scheduling problem (FJSP) in a customer-centric production system	FJSP in a make-to-order production system	Multi-objective discrete firefly algorithm (MO-DFA)	MATLAB	Optimization	A framework that allows product customization and customer-centric manufacturing	The potential and limitations of MO-DFA require further analysis	Studying the scalability of MO-DFFA and its combinations with other local search procedures
Dias et al. (2021)	To use choice-based questions and MCDA to study the preferences of a population for vehicle technologies	Vehicle technologies	MCDA MILP	Not mentioned	Data analytics optimization	The use of simple mathematical formulations to obtain the most typical value-function shapes and a post-optimization step to avoid extreme cases	The results are based on a single study about a specific situation	Simulating the diffusion of new products and technologies with system dynamics or multiagents
Garcia-Arca et al. (2021)	To propose a methodology to support decision making in packaging system design to reduce costs	Sustainable packaging logistics (SPL)	PDCA (Plan-Do-Check-Act) Heuristics	Not mentioned	Data analytics	To define, compare and select an efficient and sustainable packaging range in terms of purchase, logistics and environmental costs	A few method implementations (only one company)	Extending this methodology to three-level packaging systems
Manresa et al. (2021)	To analyze the relation between implementing new technologies and organizational practices in operational performance	Digitization	Exploratory cross-sectional questionnaires and statistics	Not mentioned	Data analytics	Showing how digitization and organizational practices differ from operational performance instead of focusing on financial performance	Low response rates and focusing on a single country: Spain	Testing the relations between the number and extent of using digitization and organizational practices and other firm performance aspects to carry out a cross-country study
Monteiro et al. (2021)	To sequentially maximize the number of pairs to be transplanted with those that have been waiting longer	Health	MILP Greedy algorithm	Python GUROBI	Optimization Simulation	Using waiting time as a criterion to select pairs to be matched cuts the maximum waiting time by slightly reducing the total number of	The use of only simple Greedy algorithms	To test more complex solution algorithms

Authors (year)	Objectives	Application context	Modeling Approach	Software tools	I4.0 technologies contributed	Major outcomes	Limitations	Future research
						transplants		
Munoz-Villamizar et al. (2021)	To present a toolkit that adapts lean tools to technological devices, training strategies and optimization to enhance and speed up environmental and production improvement	Agri-food	Serious games, e-VSM (environmental value stream mapping), OEE (overall equipment effectiveness), OGP (overall greenness performance), multi-objective approach	Pizz@green Plug&Glean	Optimization Real-time communication	Adding environmental language to traditional improvement systems to simultaneously improve production and environmental efficiencies	Validation results are not presented	To validate the proposed framework in real-world companies
Novais et al. (2021)	To propose a methodology for strategic simulation where system dynamics models use results from structural equation models (SEM)	Community cloud, information technology integration and lean/just-in-time practices	System dynamics	Vensim	Simulation	The inclusion of a dynamic analysis to the traditional SEM methodology	A few tests and applications have been carried out	To do new tests in more complex SEMs based on real-world companies
Rius-Sorolla et al. (2021)	To present a test bed generator and an instances database for a rolling horizon analysis with alternatives processes, multistroke and multicapacity	Multiechelon and multiproduct operations planning	MILP	GUROBI, Statgraphics Centurion XVII®	Optimization Simulation	The analysis of how different demand patterns influence the costs of operations planning and service level	Uncertainty factors have not been considered	To consider independent or dependent variables, such as instability and contemplate co-products or more complex products
Uribetxebarría et al. (2021)	To study the effect of participation on employee well-being and organizational performance	Human resource management	Exploratory cross-sectional Questionnaires and statistics	Not mentioned	Data analytics	Empirical results about the positive impact of HR participation in management performance indicators. Company size and productivity have provided correlations to be further studied	The nature of the considered variables and how they are measured, and the existence of alternative mechanisms	To use multiple data sources and respondents to mitigate the common method variance (CMV) issue, measurement separation in time to better evaluate causality, and to test endogenous

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Authors (year)	Objectives	Application context	Modeling Approach	Software tools	14.0 technologies contributed	Major outcomes	Limitations	Future research
							working between variables	variables at these levels
Vazquez-Noguerol et al. (2021)	To propose a model to optimize the allocation of online orders to stores based on minimising e-fulfilment costs, and also picking and delivery costs. A weighted sum method is applied to compute the optimal solution	e-grocery	MILP	MPL/GUROBI	Optimization	Consolidating workloads by avoiding idle times and reducing resources. Substantial savings made by testing in one of the largest grocery sellers	It focuses on allocating orders to vehicles, rather than managing logistics routes to travel the minimum possible kilometers	The proposed model can be adapted to other logistics configurations and decentralized approaches can be modeled
Verdecho et al. (2021a)	To propose a methodology based on MCDA for supplier selection decisions by considering sustainability performance, supply chain performance and supplier assessment criteria	Agri-food	MCDA AHP multicriteria approach	SuperDecisions©	Data analytics	To integrate the supplier selection process with supply chain sustainability management	Uncertainty factors have not been considered	To validate the proposed methodology in other real-world applications
Verdecho et al. (2021b)	To assess and manage the achievement of transversal competences at different levels of University studies (Bachelor and Master's degrees)	Education	MCDA ANP	SuperDecisions©	Data analytics	The proposal of a new approach based on integrating four components: a methodology, a performance management framework, graphical diagrams and quantitative techniques	Pairwise comparison matrices established by consensus, although there are other methods that can be applied, such as the aggregation of individual judgments or voting	To develop new tools to align the management of all study levels

4. Discussion

Regarding the papers from 2011-2020, we identified that optimization (Simoes and Marques, 2011; Ros-McDonnell et al. 2012; Garcia-Sanchez et al. 2013; Dias et al. 2014; Pastor et al. 2018; Arroyo et al. 2020; Bautista-Valhondo and Alfaro-Pozo, 2020; Leon et al. 2020; Martin et al. 2020; Mateo et al. 2020; Rius-Sorolla et al. 2020a, b; Saez-Mas, 2020), simulation (Belen et al. 2011; Baptista and Oliveira, 2012; Pedomallu et al. 2012; Pinto et al. 2012; Kovačič et al. 2015; Babiloni and Guijarro, 2020; Saez-Mas et al. 2020), data analytics (Lopez-Perez and Rodriguez-Ariza, 2013; Alvarez-Diez et al. 2014; Castro et al. 2014; Albizuri and Alvarez-Mozos, 2016; Cordero et al. (2016; Ligardo-Herrera et al. 2019; Bidosola et al. 2020; Civantos and Garcia-Algarra (2020) and machine learning (Volkovich et al. 2012; Amaro-Mellado et al. 2018; Bidosola et al. 2020) were the main I4.0 technologies contributed by Spanish and Portuguese CJOR papers. Indeed MILP (Arroyo et al. 2020; Bautista-Valhondo and Alfaro-Pozo, 2020; Mateo et al. 2020) and DEA (Simoes and Marques, 2011; Garcia-Sanchez et al. 2013; Pastor et al. 2018) were the most widely used modeling approaches in these reviewed papers. On the application context, automotive (mainly Spanish authors: Bautista-Valhondo and Alfaro-Pozo, 2020; Martin et al. 2020; Saez-Mas, 2020), health (mainly Portuguese authors: Simoes and Marques 2011; Baptista and Oliveira, 2012; Pedomallu et al. 2012; Dias et al. 2014) and financial market (Pinto et al. 2012; Alvarez-Diez et al. 2014) applications were the most addressed ones.

In the more recent 2021 papers, optimization (Alvarez-Gil et al. 2021; Monteiro et al. 2021; Munoz-Villamizar et al. 2021; Rius-Sorolla et al. 2021; Vazquez-Noguerol et al. 2021) and data analytics (Garcia-Arca et al 2021; Manresa et al. 2021; Uribetxebarria et al. 2021; Verdecho et al. 2021a, b) were the main I4.0 technologies contributed, followed by simulation (Novais et al. 2021) and real-time communication (Munoz-Villamizar et al. 2021). The application context is very diverse, but agri-food (Munoz-Villamizar et al. 2021; Verdecho et al. 2021a) and technological (Manresa et al. 2021; Novais et al. 2021) applications were mainly studied. As for the solver software for optimization, CPLEX was mainly used in the 2011-2020 papers, and GUROBI was the unique optimization solver that the reviewed 2021 papers mentioned. Mathematical programming languages MATLAB and GAMS were mostly applied in the 2011-2020 papers, with MATLAB, MP and Python in the 2021 papers.

According to Cañas et al. (2020), I4.0 could lead to growth in industrialization and disrupt the sustainability of existing manufacturing supply chains in terms of higher resource consumption, global warming, and climate change issues. Mula and Bogataj (2020) refer to I4.0 in relation to the cooperative digitization and coordination of industrial processes through information technologies. Recently, Manresa et al. (2021) addressed the benefits for firms of digital transformation, which are transforming manufacturing into digital companies integrated into the I4.0 term. Muñoz-Villamizar et al. (2021) integrate lean thinking, I4.0 and mathematical optimization to improve production and environmental performance in manufacturing companies.

On sustainability, Arroyo et al. (2020) attempt to motivate sustainable mobility through BEVs; del Rosario et al. (2020) relate sustainable development and OR; Leon et al. (2020) address sustainable energy supply in developing countries. Here sustainability is addressed mainly from the environmental perspective. Recently, Muñoz-Villamizar et al. (2021) also contemplate environmental sustainability practices. Uribetxebarria et al. (2021) consider

social sustainability from the HR perspective. Vazquez-Noguerol et al. (2021) address the economic sustainability of an online order fulfillment system. Recently, Garcia-Arca et al. (2021) deal with packaging from three sustainable perspectives: social, economic and environmental. Verdecho et al. (2021a) study sustainable supplier selection modeling and selection criteria approaches by considering the same three social, economic and environmental perspectives.

5. Conclusion

This paper identified and reviewed the articles published in CJOR by authors from the Iberian Peninsula during the 2011-2021 period to relate their contributions to the advances and implementations of I4.0 technologies. Indeed the sustainable concept was especially contemplated. We reviewed 47 papers that have been classified in terms of: objectives, application context, modeling approach, software tools and I4.0 technologies contributed. For more recent papers (in 2021), major outcomes, limitations and further research were also identified. Papers from the 2011-2020 period contribute mainly to the state of the art of optimization (13), simulation (10), data analytics (9), machine learning (4), big data (2), cooperative games for blockchain algorithms (2), optimization simulation (1) and RFID (1). Papers from 2021 contribute mostly to optimization (5), data analytics (5), simulation (4) and real-time communication (1).

It is important to highlight that until 2021, the reviewed papers did not explicitly mention making contributions to I4.0 technologies. It was then when the benefits of digital transformation (Manresa et al. 2021) and a framework proposal to integrate I4.0 and lean thinking were addressed (Munoz-Villamizar et al. (2021). Sustainability should be covered in an integrated manner from its three perspectives: social, environmental, and economic (Cañas et al. 2020). The sustainable concept is included in the reviewed papers from 2020, but mainly in relation to environmental aspects. In 2021, more papers contemplate sustainable thinking in their proposals from its three perspectives: social, environmental and economic. Nevertheless, more research that addresses industrial engineering problems by considering OR solutions under the sustainable I4.0 term umbrella is required.

Future research lines should center on proposing, testing and validating sustainable I4.0 conceptual, analytical, simulation, and artificial intelligence models to enable I4.0 adoption by companies and to bridge the gap between I4.0 strategy and operational implementation. More software tools for I4.0 practical applications by business leaders and decision makers are necessary. Finally, real-world validations of I4.0 implementations based on OR solutions would be welcomed, among others, that focus on additive manufacturing, autonomous vehicles and mobile robots, blockchain, cyber-physical systems (CPS), digital twins, Internet of Things (IoT) and Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), social media analytics and tracking and tracing systems (TTS).

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